

Comparative assessment of bathymetric methods using unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) high-resolution multispectral imaging

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ABSTRACT

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with multispectral sensors offer a promising, cost-effective alternative for high-resolution bathymetric mapping in dynamic coastal environments. This study evaluates the feasibility of adapting two established satellite-derived bathymetric (SDB) methods, the Stumpf (S) and Caballero-Stumpf (CS), to UAV-based multispectral imagery (UDB, UAV-Derived Bathymetry). Four UAV flights are conducted over Lluárcara (Northern Spain), capturing data from a port and an adjacent beach with varying turbidity and environmental conditions. Results indicate that the UDB_{green} model, based on the green band reflectance, consistently outperforms in accuracy the UDB_{red} model, based on the red band, with median absolute errors (MedAE) ranging from 0.41 to 0.67 m for depths up to 7 m. Conversely, UDB_{red} exhibits poor performance in these waters. A composite methodology integrating multiple UAV flights is also tested through the first UAV-based implementation of the CS compositing method, originally developed for satellite imagery to address turbidity. However, it does not yield significant accuracy improvements over the traditional S model or single-image results, highlighting the influence of environmental factors and flight-specific parameters on UDB data quality. Given these findings, and considering that UAV platforms offer key operational advantages, such as higher spatial resolution, flexible acquisition timing, and better suitability for small or cloud-prone coastal areas, there is a strong need for further validation of UAV-based techniques under varied coastal conditions.

1. Introduction

Coastal zones are among the most dynamic and productive environments, playing a key role in biodiversity support, essential ecosystem services, and the livelihoods of millions of people worldwide. Yet, these areas are increasingly vulnerable to rapid transformations driven by climate change, including accelerating sea-level rise, intensifying storm events, and increased rates of erosion (Patsch and Reineman, 2024; Wright and Thom, 2023). These shifts are particularly concerning for regions dependent on coastal tourism and port activities, where beaches and coastlines degradation directly impact local economies (Modi, 2024). Beaches, in particular, serve as critical economic assets that support local businesses and attract tourism while also providing recreational spaces and habitats (Toimil et al., 2018). Similarly, climate change impacts have significant implications for port infrastructure, with rising sea levels and more frequent extreme weather events disrupting maritime operations and threatening structural integrity (Modi,

2024). To sustain these valuable ecosystem services and economic activities, adaptive and integrated coastal management strategies are crucial. Consequently, researchers and policymakers are focused on understanding how coastal ecosystems can adapt to the challenges of global changes and continue providing vital services. In this context, scientific knowledge is essential to enhance the resilience of these vulnerable zones. Despite these efforts, significant data gaps remain regarding how different coastal environments respond to these stressors, highlighting the need for further research to develop effective management and protection strategies. Developing high-temporal-resolution assessment methods for dynamic coastal processes is essential for accurately monitoring these transformations with cost-effective solutions.

Remote sensing technologies, particularly multispectral imaging, have emerged as key tools for high-resolution coastal monitoring, enabling precise tracking of environmental changes (Çelik and Gazioğlu, 2024; Masria, 2024; Noh et al., 2024). Such technologies significantly

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expand our capacity to observe dynamic coastal ecosystems, monitor pollution, and support sustainable management (Cavanaugh et al., 2024; Ma et al., 2023; McCarthy et al., 2017). In particular, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), commonly referred to as drones, have proven especially valuable for coastal studies, delivering high spatial and temporal resolution data (Román et al., 2021, 2022, 2024a, 2024b). UAVs have been successfully used in a diverse range of coastal applications including shoreline mapping, monitoring of coastal erosion, habitat assessment, and vegetation studies (Casella et al., 2016; Gonçalves and Henriques, 2015; Papakonstantinou et al., 2016; Román et al., 2022; Shahbazi et al., 2014; Sujivakand et al., 2023; Turner et al., 2016; Ventura et al., 2017). Yet, the use of UAVs for other coastal applications, such as extracting bathymetric data using multispectral imaging, remains relatively underexplored, with limited studies testing their potential (Rossi et al., 2020; Sefercik et al., 2024).

Bathymetry, particularly in shallow coastal areas, is a fundamental parameter for coastal studies and essential for activities such as hydrography, fisheries, submarine cable installation, navigation, ports operations, beach erosion monitoring, coastal construction, managing of marine and coastal ecosystems (Ashphaq et al., 2021; Borland et al., 2021; Igbinenikaro et al., 2024; Mateo-Pérez et al., 2020; Schweiger et al., 2019; Valle-Levinson and Lwiza, 1997). However, obtaining accurate and high-resolution data in these regions remains challenging using traditional techniques, such as echo-sounders or LiDAR, which are constrained by high costs, accessibility issues, and inefficiencies in dynamic and shallow environments (Ashphaq et al., 2021; Casal et al., 2019; Jawak et al., 2015). In fact, shallow water region often referred to as the 'white ribbon' (Prampolini et al., 2020), are characterized by rapidly changing conditions, turbulence, and narrow coverage, which hinder the retrieval of precise and up-to-date bathymetric data (Alevizos and Alexakis, 2022; Wilson et al., 2022). Emerging remote sensing technologies provide innovative alternatives to overcome these challenges (Duan et al., 2024). Satellite-derived bathymetry (SDB), developed since the 1970s, has proven effective for large-scale mapping in clear water environments (Ashphaq et al., 2021; Gao, 2009; Jawak et al., 2015; Kutser et al., 2020; Said et al., 2017; Salameh et al., 2019), consistently achieving accuracies of 8–10 % root-mean-square error (RMSE) in depths up to 20 m through the estimating water depth based on the spectral attenuation of light (Mavraeidopoulos et al., 2017; Mishra et al., 2004; Mudiyansele et al., 2022). While challenges remain in turbid water conditions, recent advances in machine learning approaches and multi-sensor integration continue to expand SDB applicability across diverse coastal environments. However, SDB techniques often lack the resolution needed for fine-scale mapping in smaller coastal areas. UAVs equipped with multispectral sensors have adapted similar spectral methodologies to capture high-resolution, spatially detailed bathymetric data at a lower cost. These non-invasive approaches are particularly advantageous for mapping shallow, dynamic environments, offering greater accessibility, more frequent updates, and the flexibility to operate in conditions where traditional methods prove inadequate (Agrafiotis et al., 2019; Starek and Giessel, 2017).

Different UAV techniques and methodologies to retrieve bathymetry have been developed along the last years including Structure-from-Motion (SfM) to generate 3D models of shallow water environments (David et al., 2021; Dietrich, 2016; Casella et al., 2016); small topo-bathymetric laser profilers (Mandlbürger et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2022); wave-based inversion for video imagery (Santos et al., 2022, 2023); Additionally, advancements in machine learning techniques, such as Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Artificial Neural Network (ANN) or Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) have been explored for UAV-based bathymetry (Agrafiotis et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2019; Lewicka et al., 2022; McLaren et al., 2019). These techniques aim to model the relationships between multispectral reflectance and water depth, offering improved adaptability and accuracy in complex coastal environments (Agrafiotis et al., 2019); however, a considerable amount of in situ data is required to train the algorithms. Together, these

methodologies represent a promising foundation for leveraging UAVs in high-resolution, cost-effective bathymetric studies, although further research is needed to refine their application under diverse environmental conditions.

UAVs equipped with cost-effective and lightweight RGB cameras have become standard tools for bathymetric retrieval in coastal studies (Alevizos et al., 2022; Apicella et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2019; Slocum et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2024). These cameras are widely used due to their affordability, accessibility, and simplicity; however, they are limited by their lower spectral resolution, capturing only the visible red, green, and blue bands (Rump et al., 2011). This restricts their ability to differentiate subtle variations in underwater features, particularly in complex or turbid environments. In contrast, multispectral sensors offer significant advantages, such as higher dynamic ranges and customizable spectral characteristics, allowing the capture of multiple bands beyond the visible spectrum. Additionally, these sensors can be adjusted to specific spectral ranges, enabling more detailed analysis of underwater light attenuation and bottom reflectance. While traditionally bulkier, more expensive, and lower in resolution compared to RGB cameras, recent technological advancements have made lightweight multispectral sensors specifically designed for UAVs commercially available (Whitehead and Hugenholtz, 2014). These developments have expanded their potential for high-resolution remote sensing applications (Nebiker et al., 2016; Rossi et al., 2020).

Despite these advancements, the application of multispectral UAV imagery for bathymetric mapping remains a nascent field, with limited studies demonstrating its potential. The majority of current literature has focused on satellite-based multispectral sensors, which, while effective for large-scale assessments, often lack the resolution and flexibility required for fine-scale bathymetric mapping in small, dynamic coastal environments. A few pioneering studies have shown promising results by adapting satellite-derived bathymetry methods to UAV platforms. These methods utilize the principles of the Beer-Lambert Law, which describes the wavelength-dependent exponential attenuation of light through the water column, to develop models for depth estimation. These approaches have been adapted for UAV applications to estimate depths in clear, shallow waters (Rossi et al., 2020; Specht et al., 2022). For instance, Alevizos et al. (2022) employed the open-source software WASI, which features an intuitive graphical user interface designed for analyzing radiometrically corrected multiband imagery. This approach, based on end-member analysis, successfully derived depths up to 6 m with a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.69 m. Rossi et al. (2020) applied the Lyzenga (Lyzenga et al., 2006) and Stumpf (Stumpf et al., 2003) models to both UAV-derived multispectral images and satellite-based multispectral imagery. The study concluded that these models are suitable for routine monitoring of sensitive coastal zones, as they produced accurate results for shallow waters with a homogeneous seabed sediment type. Furthermore, the research highlighted that UAV-derived bathymetry tends to be more accurate than satellite-derived approaches due to the higher level of detail in the UAV imagery. However, challenges such as turbidity, bottom heterogeneity, and the limited spectral range of certain UAV sensors have yet to be systematically addressed. This lack of comprehensive studies underlines the need for further research into UAV-based multispectral techniques and their capacity to overcome the limitations of traditional and satellite-based methods.

To contribute to this emerging field, this study proposes the adaptation of two SDB models, the Stumpf (S), (2003) and the Caballero and Stumpf (CS) approach (2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2023), to high-resolution UAV-based multispectral imagery. While both methods have been widely applied in satellite remote sensing, their implementation with UAV data remains largely unexplored. In particular, the CS approach, originally developed to reduce turbidity effects and enhance bathymetric accuracy in optically complex waters, has not been tested under UAV acquisition conditions. This study presents the first UAV-based application of that methodology, offering an opportunity to evaluate

its performance under variable environmental conditions and operational constraints typical of UAV surveys. Additionally, the suitability of the UDB_{green} model (i.e., the blue-to-green band reflectance ratio adapted to UAV imagery) is examined for shallow depth retrieval (up to 7 m), where UAV platforms offer greater spatial detail than satellite imagery. By analyzing four UAV flights over a coastal zone in Luarca (Northern Spain), encompassing both a port and a natural beach with contrasting turbidity levels, this work aims to assess the comparative

performance of both models. Ultimately, this research seeks to identify the strengths and limitations of each approach when transferred from satellite to UAV platforms and to provide practical guidance for advancing UAV-based bathymetric mapping in dynamic nearshore environments.

Fig. 1. a) and b): Location of the study showing the Luarca beach (1) and the Luarca Port (2). Subfigures c, d, e, and f show the RGB images captured during the UAV flights conducted in April, May, July, and November 2023, respectively. Additionally, these subfigures include the tracks of the in situ data collection campaigns used to validate the data from each flight.

2. Study zone

The area selected to evaluate the UAV-derived images to obtain bathymetric data comprised two zones named: (1) the Luarda beach, and (2) the Luarda Port (Fig. 1b). This area is situated along the northern coast of Spain in the Principality of Asturias, holds a strategic position on the Bay of Biscay, granting it direct access to prominent national and international maritime routes. This connectivity facilitates the movement of goods and bolsters the fishing industry, which is essential to the Asturian economy.

Luarda port is a critical regional hub for economic activities, including trade and fishing, integral to the Asturian economy (Lara et al., 2019). Its advantageous location within a natural harbor, while offering protection, also leads to persistent sedimentation issues that require ongoing dredging to maintain adequate navigable depths (Mateo-Pérez et al., 2020). Addressing these challenges is critical for Luarda Port's long-term operational efficiency and accessibility, as sediment accumulation can severely impede trade and port functionality. Consequently, accurate bathymetric mapping and effective sediment management are essential in this area. Advanced techniques, such as UAV-derived bathymetric imaging, are increasingly vital for monitoring sediment transport and assessing topographic changes within the harbor, which aligns with broader regulatory pressures surrounding dredging and coastal management (Mateo-Pérez et al., 2020). Beyond its economic and environmental roles, the port's historical significance and close integration within the local community also contribute to its cultural heritage value. This multifaceted importance—encompassing its economic, environmental, and cultural dimensions—underscores the need for innovative and sustainable practices. -makers, ensuring its continued contribution to the region. As such, Luarda Port serves as an ideal site for evaluating the practical utility of UAV-derived bathymetry, providing valuable insights for regional stakeholders and decision-makers, and ensuring the port's continued contribution to the region.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Data

3.1.1. UAV-derived images

The UAV used in this study is the DJI Matrice 300 RTK, equipped with four electric motors and capable of carrying a maximum payload of 2.7 kg. It has a total weight of 6.3 kg when equipped with two TB60 LiPo 12S batteries, each with a capacity of 5 935 mAh and a voltage of 52.8 V. The drone's take-off weight is limited to 9.0 kg. The multi-spectral camera employed for data collection was the Micasense RedEdge-MX, which captured five spectral bands: blue (475 nm), green (560 nm), red (668 nm), red edge (717 nm), and near-infrared (842 nm). A calibration panel (RP06-2120491-OB) and a DLS2 with integrated GPS were used to ensure accurate data collection. Calibration was performed before and after each flight by capturing images at a height of 1 m from the calibration panel, with particular care taken to avoid shadows. Flight parameters, such as altitude, overlap, and speed, were planned using the DJI Pilot software installed on the UAV controller. Throughout the study, the flight altitude was set to 100 m for most sessions, except for the flight on May 25, 2023, which was conducted at an altitude of 120 m. Longitudinal and transverse overlaps were consistently set at 70 % and 80 %, respectively, with flight speeds varying from 4 m/s to 10 m/s depending on the specific session.

Agisoft Metashape v.1.8.3 (Agisoft LLC, St. Petersburg, Russia) was used to process the multispectral images for the generation of orthomosaics from the UAV captures. This software created an orthomosaic of remote sensing reflectance (Rrs) values for each multispectral band. The reflectance values were first calibrated using the reflectance panels and the DLS, allowing for accurate radiometric corrections. The pictures were then aligned to create a precise 3D model of the area. Camera

optimization was performed to refine the positions and orientations of each image, enhancing the overall accuracy of the model. A dense cloud was built to capture detailed information about the terrain's surface, followed by the creation of a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) to represent the topography. An orthomosaic was generated based on the DEM, with the coordinate system set to ETRS89/UTM 29N (EPSG:25 829) for accurate georeferencing. Raster transformation was applied to maintain the integrity of the reflectance values, ensuring that the output bands were in 16-bit integer format. The middle value of the range (32 768) was set to represent 100 % reflectance for each band. If reflectance normalization was required, the formula $B1/32\ 768$; $B2/32\ 768$; $B3/32\ 768$; $B4/32\ 768$; $B5/32\ 768$ was used in the Raster Calculator. Finally, the orthomosaic was exported as a georeferenced TIFF file, with pixel size set to 6–8 cm and the highest resolution possible, ensuring accurate spatial representation of the area.

3.1.2. Single-beam echo sounder data

For the acquisition of bathymetric data, a recreational vessel was used, specifically a Merry Nautic Teychan 540 Timonerie model, measuring 5.40 m in length and 2.35 m in beam. The vessel was equipped with a Reson TC2122 single-beam echo sounder (SBES), installed on the port side of the boat, at the end of a 2.11-m stainless steel mast. This transducer is capable of recording depth data at two frequencies, 33 kHz and 200 kHz, and is controlled through a Navisound 215 single-beam echo sounder system, also from Reson. The positioning system used for the data acquisition consisted of two Leica 1 200-series GPS-RTK units: one installed on land at a known coordinate point, in the ETRS89 reference system (UTM29 projection), while the other was mounted on top of the mast of the boat. Real-time differential corrections were transmitted via radio, allowing the system to record the antenna's three-dimensional position (X, Y, Z_{antenna}) with centimeter-level accuracy at a frequency of 20 Hz. Both the echo sounder and GPS-RTK systems recorded data at a frequency of 20 Hz, which were transmitted in real-time to a laptop. The navigation lines were planned, and the data was stored and processed using the Hypack 2010 software package (HYPACK), allowing for precise control and post-processing of the bathymetric measurements. During post-processing, depth measurements were filtered to remove defective echoes and adjusted for the vertical offset between the antenna and the transducer. The final dataset contains bathymetric points (X, Y, Z_{bathymetry}) referenced to the hydrographic zero of the Port of Luarda, which closely matches the BMVE benchmark. Field surveys were conducted on 26 April, 25 May, 26 July, and November 16, 2023, with GPS-RTK start/end times and antenna heights detailed in Table 1 (average heights ranged from 1.27 m to 3.19 m).

3.2. Methodology

The methodology was organized into two main processes: Pre-processing and UAV-derived Bathymetry (UDB) implementing both the Stumpf et al. (2003) model, and the Caballero and Stumpf (2019, 2020a, 2020b) model, hereinafter referred to as S method and CS method, respectively, for further comparison (Fig. 2).

3.2.1. Pre-processing

The original spatial resolution was reduced from 8 cm/pixel to 40

Table 1
SBES campaign data. GPS-RTK system time and elevation data.

	26-04-2023	25-05-2023	26-07-2023	16-11-2023
Start time	12:44	11:13	12:16	12:23
End time	13:58	12:43	13:30	13:27
Start height	2.79 m	2.98 m	3.41 m	1.33 m
End height	2.37 m	2.29 m	2.97 m	1.22 m
Average height	2.58 m	2.61 m	3.19	1.27

Fig. 2. Workflow diagram illustrating the methodology applied in this study.

cm/pixel by calculating the mean Rrs within a 5×5 grid centered on each original pixel. This step ensured computational efficiency and reduced noise. Sun glint, a significant challenge in water remote sensing, was addressed by selecting the best-performing among three established approaches: Joyce (2004), Hedley et al. (2005), and Lyzenga et al. (2006). All methods rely on the near infrared (NIR) band's sensitivity to sun glint, assuming near-zero NIR values in deep water without sun glint. Pixels with $NIR > 0$ are thus identified as sun glint-affected. To correct sun glint in the visible (VIS) green, red, and blue bands, a homogeneous deep-water area with visible sun glint was manually defined, and Equation (1) was applied to adjust Rrs in the affected pixels:

$$R(VIS)' = R(VIS) - b[R(NIR) - m(NIR)] \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where $R(VIS)'$ is the corrected Rrs for each VIS band, $R(VIS)$ is the original Rrs for each VIS band, $R(NIR)$ is the NIR Rrs for the entire image, b represents the relationship between each VIS band and the NIR band, and $m(NIR)$ is a statistical value derived from the $R(NIR)$ of the selected area.

In Hedley's method, b is the slope of the linear regression between the NIR values of the selected area and each VIS band, resulting in separate slopes for blue, green, and red bands. The $m(NIR)$ value is defined as the minimum Rrs value of NIR in the selected area. In Lyzenga's method, b represents the covariance between each VIS band and NIR, while $m(NIR)$ is the mean NIR Rrs . For Joyce's method, b is also derived as the slope of the linear regression between the VIS and NIR bands, with $m(NIR)$ defined as the mode of NIR Rrs .

3.2.2. UAV-derived bathymetric models

Two well-known SDB models were adapted for use with UAV imagery: The S model (Stumpf et al., 2003), and the CS model (Caballero and Stumpf, 2019, 2020a, 2020b). Both methods establish a near-linear relationship between reflectance and depth by utilizing the ratio of log-transformed spectral bands with differing absorption properties. These models are widely recognized for their minimal calibration requirements and applicability across various sensor.

3.2.2.1. S method. According to Stumpf et al. (2003), the UDB (UAV-Derived Bathymetry) from each image corresponding of each flight was derived using the following equations:

$$UDB = m_1(pUDB - pUDB_0) \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

$$pUDB = \frac{\ln(n\pi Rrs(\lambda_i))}{\ln(n\pi Rrs(\lambda_j))} \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

Where, UDB represents the depth in meters, while pUDB represents a dimensionless pseudo-depth obtained from UAV imagery. The parameters λ_i and λ_j refer to the blue band and the green band, respectively,

enabling the derivation of $pUDB_{Green}$. The term $pUDB_0$ is defined by the ratio of m_1/m_0 which align algebraically with the equation presented by Stumpf et al. (2003). In this equation m_0 and m_1 are constants determined through calibration, Rrs denotes the remote sensing reflectance (sr^{-1}), and n set to 1000, is a constant ensuring positivity in logarithmic computations. After calculating each pUDB, actual depth values were determined using a linear regression method as outlined by Stumpf et al. (2003). Approximately 45 calibration points, randomly selected within a designated area identified as clear and suitable for calibration (see shaded polygons in Fig. 3), were used to produce the final UDB_{Green} . These values were derived from the images obtained during the UAV flights conducted in April, May, June, and November 2023.

3.2.2.2. CS method. Depth calculations were initiated using the log-transformed band ratio model introduced by Stumpf et al. (2003) (Equations (2) and (3)), which utilizes the ratio of Rrs in the blue (475 nm) and green (560 nm) bands, effective for depths up to 25 m. To enhance performance in shallow waters (depths < 7 m), the model was extended by incorporating the blue (475 nm) to red (668 nm) band ratio, following the approach proposed by Caballero and Stumpf (2019). In this adaptation, the parameters λ_i and λ_j in Equation (3) represent the blue and the red bands, respectively, allowing for the calculation of $pUDB_{Red}$.

To address turbidity and other artifacts like clouds, sun glint, and shadows that can affect SDB, we adopted the compositing methodology by Caballero and Stumpf (2020a, 2020b). For satellites, this technique uses several images and evaluates each pixel across all the scenes, selecting the one with the least turbidity impact, thereby generating a composite image of pseudo-bathymetry (pSDB) with minimal distortions. The resulting composite image is adjusted to actual depths using a linear transformation (Stumpf et al., 2003) and further calibrated with in situ data points. The final step of this methodology is applying a Switching model developed by Caballero and Stumpf (2020a, 2020b, 2023), which combines the strength of SDB_{green} for deeper waters and SDB_{red} for shallow areas, assuring accurate depth estimation across varying depths ranges. In this study, we extended this methodology to UAV-derived imagery for the first time. Unlike satellite images, where pixel dimensions are consistent across scenes, each UAV flight covered a different area with varying pixel sizes. To address this, the final composite image was standardized to the dimensions of the smallest image (May 2023). Once the base size was determined, the same compositing procedure was applied, comparing each pixel across the UAV images and selecting the one least affected by turbidity. More detailed information on this procedure can be found in Caballero and Stumpf (2020a, 2020b, 2023).

3.2.2.2.1. Validation. Given the critical importance of accuracy assessment in SDB for coastal management and marine applications, the results were validated using SBES data, with in situ measurements from

Fig. 3. A common zone (shaded area) was delineated, and only a selected subset of in situ data points within this zone was used for model calibration for each flight, ensuring consistency and comparability. The trajectories and corresponding depth variations from the in situ surveys are shown for each flight, conducted in a) April, b) May, c) July, and d) November 2023, to support the corresponding validation.

each zone employed for single-image analysis. Three complementary statistical indicators, Median Absolute Error (MedAE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), were strategically selected to evaluate model performance. This integrated use of complementary metrics follows established validation protocols (Poursanidis et al., 2019; Caballero and Stumpf, 2020a) and enables a comprehensive assessment of model reliability, contributing to improved methodological standards for UAV-based bathymetric mapping. Additionally, scatter plots and residual histograms were analyzed to assess the accuracy of the results.

4. Results

The RGB images captured during the four UAV flights in April, May, July and November 2023 exhibited varying visual characteristics, as shown in Fig. 1c, d, 1e, 1f. Based on tide tables (<https://tablademareas.com/>), the flights in April, May, and July were carried out near high tide conditions, while the November flight took place closer to low tide. The water level difference between the high tide sessions was minimal, with a variation of less than 20 cm. Differences in water clarity and image resolution are evident across the dataset. The May flight (Fig. 1d), in particular, displays areas within the water body where data is missing, alongside noticeable surface distortions caused by wind. In contrast,

some images from other flights show clearer seafloor visibility, suggesting more favorable conditions during data collection. Overall, these observations highlight the role of environmental variability in leading to inconsistent visual properties across the different flight sessions.

A comparative analysis of sunglint correction methods was conducted on UAV-derived imagery from four different flight sessions, applying the deglint algorithms proposed by Joyce (2004), Hedley et al. (2005), and Lyzenga et al. (2006). The performance of each method was evaluated through visual inspection, focusing on the effective removal of sunglint-related artifacts such as ships, shadows or ground. As shown in Fig. 4, Hedley's method was the most effective in masking these disturbances, substantially improving image interpretability and preserving submerged features. In contrast, Lyzenga's algorithm appeared ineffective for these images, yielding minimal visual changes and failing to attenuate sunglint. Both Hedley and Joyce methods performed similarly, successfully identifying and masking pixels affected by excessive sunglint or those misclassified as water. Based on these observations and its widespread use in the remote sensing literature (Windle and Silsbe, 2021), Hedley's algorithm was selected for further processing in this study.

The S method, commonly applied for SDB, was applied to single UAV-derived images, utilizing the ratio between blue and green reflectance (UDB_{green}). Additionally, the novel CS method, which incorporates

Fig. 4. Comparative results of sunglint correction applied to UAV-derived imagery from each flight during 2023. Subfigures a.1, b.1, c.1 and d.1 correspond to the original RGB images. Subfigures a.2, b.2, c.2 and d.2 show results after applying the Hedley's deglint method, while a.3, b.3, c.3 and d.3 correspond to the Lyzenga's deglint method and a.4, b.4, c.4 and d.4 illustrate the application of the Joyce's deglint algorithms.

the blue-to-red reflectance ratio (UDB_{red}) and a compositing approach, was also evaluated for comparison. Although UDB_{red} is not required for the S method, calibration equations for both UDB_{green} and UDB_{red} were derived for each flight session to assess their behavior and enable comparisons with the CS method, which employs the blue-to-red reflectance ratio using composited imagery. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the calibration equations for single images revealed a clear linear relationship between in situ data and the $pUDB_{green}$, with coefficient of correlation (R^2) values ranging from approximately 0.5 to 0.8. The highest correlation was observed during the July flight. In contrast, the $pUDB_{red}$ exhibited no significant correlation, with R^2 values consistently below 0.21, indicating poor agreement with in situ measurements.

After calibrating the UDB_{green} and UDB_{red} models and deriving the bathymetry from the UAV imagery, a comprehensive statistical analysis was conducted to rigorously validate model performance against in situ measurements, as shown in the scatter plots in Fig. 6. The analysis reveals a much closer agreement between the depths obtained from the UDB_{green} model and the in situ measurements, with data points clustering tightly around the 1:1 reference line (Fig. 6a.1, 6.a.2, 6.a.3 and 6.a.4). In contrast, the UDB_{red} model exhibited poor correlation, with

points scattered far from the reference line, reflecting its limited reliability in estimating depths (Fig. 6c.1, 6.c.2, 6.c.3 and 6.c.4). This reduced correlation was consistent across the four UAV-derived scenes analyzed.

The residual histograms for UDB_{green} indicate a predominantly unimodal normal distribution centered around zero (Fig. 6b.1, 6.b.2, 6.b.3 and 6.b.4), except for the April 2023 image (Fig. 6b.1), where a bimodal distribution emerges for both models. One peak is centered near zero, while another indicates systematic overestimation of depths. This anomaly may be caused by the influence of environmental factors, such as turbidity or surface reflectance distortions, or operational inconsistencies during that specific flight. Statistical analysis yielded MedAE values ranging from 0.41 m to 0.67 m, and MAE values below 0.9 m for depths up to 7 m, with the November 2023 flight producing the lowest errors relative to in situ data. In addition to these favorable statistical results, the scatter plots show a higher density of points clustered around the 1:1 reference line for UDB_{green} . However, for the April 2023 dataset, while a significant portion of the points lies near the 1:1 line, a notable subset shows an overestimation of very shallow depths derived from the UAV images compared to the in situ measurements, which is

Fig. 5. Scatter plots showing individual calibrations for pUDBgreen (a.1, b.1, c.1 and d.1) and pUDBred (a.2, b.2, c.2 and d.2) corresponding to each flight conducted in 2023.

consistent with the bimodal trend observed in the residuals. This pattern is further supported by Fig. 7, which displays the spatial distribution of UDB-in situ differences across all UAV scenes. In the April image (Fig. 7a), overestimations (green color) are located near the boat ramp, while other datasets (May, July and November) exhibit spatially coherent underestimations (brown colors) in deeper areas, revealing consistent spatial patterns of model bias.

In the case of UDB_{red}, both the scatter plots (Fig. 6b.1, 6.b.2, 6.b.3 and 6.b.4) and residual histograms (Fig. 6d.1, 6.d.2, 6.d.3 and 6.d.4) indicate higher statistical errors compared to UDB_{green}. The bimodal nature observed in the April 2023 image persists (Fig. 6d.1), reflecting a clear overestimation of depths in one of the peaks. Although the May 2023 scene (Fig. 6c.2) shows a significant density of points clustered around the 1:1 reference line, with MedAE and MAE values of 0.63 m and 0.92 m for depths up to 5m, respectively, the remaining images exhibit a lower density of points close to the reference line, highlighting the unsuccessful performance of the model. This lack of a consistent point distribution suggests that the depth estimations derived from the UDB_{red} model in most of the flights are not as trustworthy as those obtained using the UDB_{green} model.

In addition to testing the S method, the CS method, which includes a composite approach, was also evaluated. The original CS method developed by Caballero and Stumpf (2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2023) included UDB_{green} and UDB_{red} using a composited image to further apply the switching approach. However, the UDB maps were derived only using the UDB_{green} model, as they demonstrated the best performance, both for individual images and for the composite (Figs. 6 and 8).

Fig. 9e displaying the composited UDB_{green} provides a clear visual representation of the bathymetry across the entire area, with only a limited number of in situ points used to calibrate the models. The transition from shallower to deeper zones is evident, and there is strong agreement between the derived bathymetries and the in situ data.

However, the composite image did not provide any improvement over the individual images, as confirmed by the statistical analysis (Table 2). Fig. 8a.1 illustrates the calibration equation for the composite model. Once calibrated, a statistical assessment was conducted, and the scatter plots and histograms comparing UDB against in situ data reveal that the UDB_{green} model outperforms the UDB_{red} model. The scatter plot for UDB_{green} (Fig. 8b.1) indicates that there is no significant enhancement when using the composite model compared to the individual images; in fact, the errors associated with the composite model are notably higher, with MedAE and MAE values of 0.77 m and 1.31 m, respectively, for depths up to 7 m. This analysis shows a major density of points that both overestimate and underestimate the depths in relation to the in situ measurements (Fig. 8b.1 and 8.b.2). The histogram of residuals for the composite model exhibits a much wider distribution compared to those corresponding to the individual image analyses, further confirming the reduced reliability of the composite methodology in this context (Fig. 8c.1 and 8.c.2).

Although the influence of environmental conditions was not quantitatively assessed in this study, differences in model performance appeared to align with variations in flight settings. The November flight, conducted near low tide and under turbid water conditions, yielded the lowest MedAE (0.41 m) for UDB_{green}. In contrast, the April flight, despite presenting higher visual clarity, resulted in a bimodal error distribution and a higher MedAE (0.65 m). While this single observation suggests a possible link between acquisition conditions and model accuracy, further research is needed to systematically evaluate the impact of environmental variability on bathymetric accuracy.

5. Discussion

This study assessed the efficacy of UAV-derived multispectral imagery for shallow water bathymetry, demonstrating its capacity for high-

Fig. 6. Statistical results comparing UDB_{green} and UDB_{red} values and the corresponding in situ data for each flight. Subfigures a.1, a.2, a.3 and a.4 correspond to scatterplots between UDB_{green} and in situ data. Subfigures c.1, c.2, c.3 and c.4 correspond to scatterplots between UDB_{red} and in situ data. Subfigures b.1, b.2, b.3 and b.4 represent the residual error for UDB_{red} data and subfigures d.1, d.2, d.3 and d.4 represent the residual error for UDB_{red} data.

resolution, cost-effective depth estimation in dynamic coastal environments. The analysis revealed that S and CS models yielded distinct levels of accuracy, with the UDB_{green} model consistently outperforming the UDB_{red} model in terms of correlation with in situ data. Across the four UDB images, the UDB_{green} model achieved MedAE values ranging from 0.41 m to 0.67 m, and MAE values below 0.9 m for depths up to 7 m. In contrast, the composite UDB_{green} model exhibited slightly higher error metrics, with a MedAE of 0.77 m and a MAE of 1.31 m. This result indicates that the composite methodology using multiple UAV flights did not significantly improve bathymetric accuracy over individual images, underscoring the sensitivity of UDB accuracy to environmental conditions and flight-specific technical settings.

The superior performance of the UDB_{green} model aligns with prior studies demonstrating the reliability of green band reflectance for shallow water depth estimation, particularly in satellite-derived applications (Caballero and Stumpf, 2019), and extends this efficacy to UAV-based multispectral imagery. Alevizos et al. (2022) successfully mapped depths up to 10 m, achieving (RMSE of 0.2–0.5 m depending on water clarity and the density of calibration data. Their findings

emphasize the green band's superior penetration of the water column and its consistent performance in depth estimations across various platforms, including both satellite and UAV imagery, particularly in low-turbidity conditions. The UDB_{red} , in contrast, showed poor performance in this study. This was particularly evident in the July 2023 datasets, which featured more complex environmental conditions (Figs. 5 and 6), highlighting the limitations of longer wavelengths, such as those in the red, which have lower penetration in water and greater susceptibility to scattering (Alevizos et al., 2022; Specht et al., 2022). These results not only reinforce the value of UAV-based multispectral approaches but also highlight the green band's critical role in achieving high-resolution and accurate bathymetric mapping in dynamic coastal zones.

One of the aims of this study was to evaluate the performance of the UDB_{red} model, given the promising results previously reported for the SDB_{red} model using Sentinel-2 imagery in shallower waters (<5 m), particularly within switching model frameworks (e.g., Caballero and Stumpf, 2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2023; Viana-Borja et al., 2023, 2024). However, the UDB_{red} results were unexpectedly poor, suggesting

Fig. 7. Spatial distribution of the residuals between UAV-derived bathymetry (UDB) and in situ single-beam echo sounder (SBES) measurements for each UAV flight session: (a) April, (b) May, (c) July, and (d) November 2023. The residuals are calculated as UDB minus SBES, with brown color indicating underestimation and blue color indicating overestimation of depth. The maps reveal spatial and temporal variability in model accuracy, highlighting areas of consistent error patterns across different flight conditions. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

potential limitations when adapting red-band approaches to UAV imagery. This discrepancy may stem from spectral and radiometric differences between UAV multispectral sensors and satellite platforms like Sentinel-2. For instance, UAV sensors often exhibit variations in red band placement and bandwidth, which could affect water column penetration and increase sensitivity to surface scattering (Alevizos et al., 2022). Furthermore, UAV imagery's higher spatial resolution—while advantageous—can accentuate noise from transient surface features such as glint, ripples, or floating matter, which are typically averaged out in coarser satellite imagery (Casal et al., 2019; Alevizos et al., 2022). These factors underscore the need for platform-specific calibration and performance evaluation when transferring bathymetric models from satellite to UAV platforms (Dekker et al., 2011; Kutser et al., 2020).

As highlighted by Santos et al. (2023), variations in environmental conditions, such as water clarity and surface reflectivity, can profoundly influence UAV-derived imagery quality and the precision of bathymetric outputs. This study's flights conducted in April, May, July and November 2023 demonstrated these challenges, with significant variability observed across datasets. For instance, during the May flight, increased wind led to surface distortions and reduced seafloor visibility, consistent with previous studies showing that wind-driven surface roughness can increase sun glint and surface reflections, thereby

interfering with bottom detection and increasing uncertainty in bathymetric retrieval (Kay et al., 2009; Zeng et al., 2017). The flights in April, May, and July were conducted near high tide, while the November flight took place closer to low tide. Viana-Borja et al. (2024) discuss how tidal variations can affect SDB, noting that images captured during low tide may provide better results. This aligns with our results, where the November flight, conducted near low tide, yielded the best performance in terms of bathymetric accuracy, with the lowest values of MAE and MedAE. Despite calmer weather conditions during the July flight, its bathymetric outputs were less accurate. This disparity suggests that tidal stage may influence water column transparency or bottom reflectance. Importantly, the composited model, built from images acquired under both high and low tide, showed degraded performance, potentially due to these inconsistencies across scenes. This highlights the need for further research to assess the influence of tidal state and surface conditions on UAV-derived bathymetry, as current literature on this subject remains scarce.

A notable observation within the April 2023 dataset was a bimodal trend in the residuals, indicating a systematic overestimation of very shallow depths (<2 m) derived from the UAV images compared to in situ measurements. While SDB in extremely shallow waters is often challenged by high variability due to light attenuation and substrate effects

Fig. 8. a.1, a.2) Calibration equations derived from the composite model data, along with scatter plots (b.1, b.2) illustrating the relationship between in situ measurements and UDB_{green} and UDB_{red} values from the composite model. c.1, c.2) histograms displaying the distribution of residual errors.

(Lyzenga, 1978; Stumpf et al., 2003), recent studies have shown that overestimation of depth, particularly when using green-band algorithms in clear, shallow conditions, is a common occurrence (Caballero and Stumpf, 2019, 2020a; Viana-Borja et al., 2023, 2024). This overestimation in our study, critically located in the very shallow area surrounding the boat ramp as depicted in Fig. 7 (area delimited by a red square), likely stems from a combination of environmental and technical factors during the April flight. The flight was performed under high tide conditions and calm skies with high sun elevation, which significantly increased bottom reflectance from features like the highly reflective boat ramp, artificially enhancing the green-band signal. In very shallow waters, the green band's reduced sensitivity to subtle depth changes and its tendency to saturate in response to high bottom reflectance can cause the model to overestimate depth. The non-linear relationship between reflectance and depth becomes highly sensitive in very shallow waters (Alevizos et al., 2022; Casal et al., 2019), where small changes in bottom type or illumination can lead to noticeable model deviations, a behavior that appears more pronounced in high-resolution UAV imagery due to its enhanced sensitivity to minor variations in surface reflectance.

This analysis also underscores the operational advantages of UAVs in capturing high-resolution imagery at user-defined times, particularly in small or cloud-prone coastal areas. However, it highlights a critical need for objective, standardized criteria in selecting the optimal single image, as visual clarity alone did not consistently correlate with improved bathymetric accuracy. This is evidenced by the strong performance of the November dataset with high turbidity levels, which outperformed compared to the April flight despite lower turbidity levels. These findings emphasize the importance of developing automated or semi-automated selection protocols based on environmental metadata or spectral thresholds, to avoid subjective biases in operational workflows. Moreover, the integration of data-driven models, such as neural networks, may enhance the robustness of UDB estimations across a wider range of coastal conditions, particularly in environments with high turbidity or heterogeneous substrates (Lewicka et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2019). Oncoming work should prioritize expanding case studies to encompass diverse coastal typologies. Additionally, standardized UAV protocols could enhance the reliability, comparability, and scalability of UAV-derived bathymetric approaches. Future research should target

- Quantifying the effects of tidal and atmospheric variability on UAV-derived bathymetry.
- Extending case studies to estuarine and heterogeneous seabed.
- Testing machine learning and deep learning models to improve model generalizability.
- Exploring the benefit of hyperspectral UAV sensors to enhance depth retrieval in complex environments.

By addressing these challenges, UAV-based bathymetric approaches can become pivotal tools for coastal management, habitat monitoring, and environmental planning.

6. Conclusions

This study confirmed the potential of UAV-derived multispectral imagery for high-resolution, cost-effective bathymetric mapping in dynamic coastal environments. The UDB_{green} model, based on the green band reflectance, consistently outperformed the UDB_{red} model in accuracy, achieving MedAE ranging from 0.41 m to 0.67 m, with a mean MedAE of approximately 0.59 m for depths up to 7 m under varying environmental conditions. These results reaffirm the green band's reliability for depth estimation, particularly in low-turbidity environments, while highlighting the limitations of red band reflectance. Despite the promising outcomes in SDB, the composite methodology, designed to integrate multiple UAV flights, did not yield improved accuracy than optimal single-date image. This finding highlights the need for further research to understand the interactions between environmental variability, technical settings, and the accuracy of composite models. Operationally, UAVs offer flexibility in data acquisition and enable high-spatial resolution, but objective criteria for optimal image selection remain essential to avoid subjective biases. These results provide a foundation for developing standardized UAV workflows for bathymetric applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S.P. Viana-Borja: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **S. Heredia:**

Fig. 9. RGB images, UDB_{green} and UDB_{red} maps derived from the original images, and the corresponding in situ data for each flight. Additionally, the composite UDB_{green} map is included.

Visualization, Validation, Methodology. **G. Navarro:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **X. Santamarta-Benito:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **N. Araujo-Suarez:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **I. Caballero:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Table 2

Statistical analysis for both S and CS methods. Statistics (Mean Absolute Error-MAE, Median Absolute Error-MedAE, and Root Mean Square Error-RMSE) from the validation of UDBgreen and UDBred against SBES. N corresponds to the total amount of pixels used to validate each image.

S method									
Flights date	UDBgreen				UDBred				N
	MAE (m)	MedAE (m)	RMSE (m)	Depth (m)	MAE (m)	MedAE (m)	RMSE (m)	Depth (m)	
April	0.90	0.65	1.28	7	1.11	0.85	1.41	5	6 407
May	0.83	0.63	1.15	7	0.92	0.63	1.29	7	25 326
July	0.75	0.67	0.93	7	1.03	0.8	1.32	5	16 125
November	0.63	0.41	0.94	6	0.62	0.53	0.77	5	19 364

CS method									
Composite	UDBgreen				UDBred				N
	MAE (m)	MedAE (m)	RMSE (m)	Depth (m)	MAE (m)	MedAE (m)	RMSE (m)	Depth (m)	
Composite	1.31	0.77	2.14	7	1.12	0.9	1.43	5	67 221

Glossary

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

UDB UAV-Derived Bathymetry

SDB Satellite-Derived Bathymetry

S method Stumpf method. A log-ratio algorithm (Stumpf et al., 2003) based on the reflectance ratio between two bands, blue and green, to estimate bathymetry

CS method Caballero-Stumpf method. An approach that applies composite imagery and a switching model to improve bathymetry estimations in areas with varying turbidity, originally developed for satellite data (Caballero and Stumpf, 2019, 2020a, 2020b, 2023)

UDB_{green} UAV-derived bathymetry using the green band ratio (blue-to-green reflectance) from single or composite imagery

UDB_{red} UAV-derived bathymetry using the red band (blue-to-red reflectance), used in the CS method

MedAE Median Absolute Error. A robust metric representing the median of the absolute differences between predicted and observed depths

MAE Mean Absolute Error. The average of the absolute differences between predicted and measured depths

RMSE Root Mean Square Error. A common metric used to assess the accuracy of predictions in bathymetric modeling, giving more weight to larger errors

Compositing Model A method of integrating multiple images to generate a single dataset to overcome the subjectivity and time-consuming issues derived from selecting an optimal scene according to water conditions, addressing complex constraints such as turbidity and false shoaling effects (Caballero and Stumpf, 2020a, 2020b, 2023; Viana-Borja et al., 2023, 2024)

Switching Model Based on the CS method, the switching model automatically selects the optimal band ratio—either blue-to-green (UDBgreen) or blue-to-red (UDBred)—based on a depth threshold, improving bathymetric accuracy across varying optical water column conditions (Caballero and Stumpf, 2020b, 2023)

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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